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Corrosion protection of metallic bipolar plates and porous transport layers in proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer anodes

Michel Prestat, Flavien Vucko (1), Khaoula Chergui, Benoit Lescop, Stéphane Rioual (2), Ludivine Rault, Valérie Demange (3)

(1) French Corrosion Institute, Brest/France;

(2) Univ Brest, CNRS, Lab-STICC, Brest/France;

(3) Univ Rennes, CNRS, ISCR - UMR 6226, ScanMAT - UAR 2025, Rennes/France;

Tel.: +33-298-05-15-52

michel.prestat@institut-corrosion.fr

Abstract

Proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer (PEMWE) is one of the low temperature devices for producing hydrogen at industrial scale. However, the high capital expenditures (capex) due to the use of expensive corrosion-resistant materials limit the economic competitiveness of this technology compared to the well-established fossil fuel-based hydrogen production, like steam reforming, that generates intensive CO₂ emissions. In particular, on the anode side, porous transport layers (PTL) and bipolar plates (BPP), that constitute more than half of the PEMWE stack costs, are currently made of titanium protected by coatings of precious metals in order to withstand the harsh oxidizing and corrosive conditions. This short paper reviews the recent developments of BPP and PTL corrosion protection driven by capex reduction, notably the replacement of titanium by stainless steels and the application of novel, more cost-effective anti-corrosion coatings.

An extended version of this literature analysis has been recently published in the Journal of the Power Sources [1].

Introduction

One of the European Union's strategies to limit global warming and increase Europe's energy independency is to massively utilize green or decarbonized hydrogen as an energy carrier and feedstock for industry by 2050 [2]. Such hydrogen production can be achieved using water electrolysis using proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) [3-5]. A PEMWE electrochemically splits water and is made up of i) feeding plates (called "bipolar plates", hereafter denoted BPP) whose role is to transport the liquid water and evacuate the gases produced and connect the single cells in an electrolysis stack, ii) porous transport layers (PTL) which ensure the electrical connection between the BPP and the electrodes while allowing the liquid water and the gases to pass through, and iii) a catalyst coated membrane (CCM) consisting of a proton-conducting polymer electrolyte membrane on which the electrodes (catalysts) are deposited (Figure 1a).

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of the PEMWE working principle with MEM accounting for the electrolyte membrane, CL for the catalyst layers (electrodes), BPP for the bipolar plates and PTL for the porous transport layers. The catalyst-coated membrane (CCM) is the assembly of the MEM and the CL. (b) Capital expenditures breakdown in a PEMWE stack. Both sketches are adapted from [6] under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

In the anode compartment, the state-of-the-art material is titanium for withstanding the harsh operating conditions, namely the acidic PTL/catalyst/electrolyte interphase and the elevated electrochemical potential (around + 2V/SHE) [1]. Furthermore, it is known that the native titanium oxide layer (that provides the resistance to corrosion) can be destabilized under oxidizing conditions (in PEMWE [7] as well as in other industrial applications, such as biomedical implants [8-9]). A resistive oxide layer tends to grow at the titanium surface (which is evidenced by its discoloration), thereby increasing the interfacial contact resistance (ICR) between adjoining elements and decreasing the electrolysis efficiency [7,10]. In order to address this issue, noble metal coatings (Au, Pt, Ir) have been utilized against BPP and PTL corrosion [11,12]. Nevertheless, in some cases, those protective coatings peel off their substrates after several hundreds of hours of operation, resulting in the undesired pollution of the CCM and oxidation of the underlying titanium [10,12]. Furthermore, the main issue arising from the utilization of titanium structural elements coated with precious metal layers is that it negatively affects the capital expenditures (capex) of the technology. It is estimated that the BPP and PTL account for more than 60% of the capex of the PEM electrolyzer stacks, [6,13], as illustrated in Figure 1b.

Although other materials like copper have been investigated [14], stainless steels are seen as realistic alternatives for BPP and PTL materials in the next generation of more cost-effective PEMWE, especially if associated non-precious metal coatings. This conference

proceeding article highlights some of the most recent and relevant progresses going in this direction.

1. Recent progresses towards stainless steel BPP

As regards the electrochemical conditions around the BPP, the works of Becker *et al.* experimentally demonstrated that the potential of the BPP (and most of the PTL) is decoupled from the applied current density (or cell voltage) [15]. In other words, the anode side of BPP bathing in the water feed acts as a simple current collector. Hence during ex-situ corrosion testing of BPP materials (using three-electrode electrochemical cells), the potential of the BPP (with or without coating) corresponds to its corrosion potential and not to the anode potential (that is typically around 1.8 V/SHE for current density of 2 A/cm²). It must be noted, however, that the BPP potential can be shifted due to by galvanic coupling with the PTL.

Taking those findings into account in a continuing work, Becker *et al.* protected 316L stainless steel BPP with an outermost carbon film (ca. 35 nm thin) on top of an adhesion layer (ca. 100 nm thin) [16]. The chemical composition of the latter was not provided. Though the degradation rate was not negligible (11 mV/h, Figure 2), no degradation of the carbon layer was recorded with Auger electron spectroscopy analysis after 30 days of PEMWE operation at 2 A/cm² (with the cell potential being around 1.9 V/SHE) at 60°C.

Figure 2: 30-day PEMWE operation with carbon-coated 316L BPP at 60 °C. (a) PEMWE voltage as a function of time at a current density of 2 A/cm² (b) Polarization curve of the PEMWE in pristine state (0 day) and after the 30-day testing. Reproduced and adapted from [16] under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Using a thick film approach, Gago and Lettenmeier deposited titanium coatings (ca. 60 - 100 μm) by vacuum plasma spraying (VPS) [17-18]. The titanium was protected from oxidation by a top-layer of platinum or niobium. The coatings were porous (with pore sizes up to ca. 10 μm) and required a sealing step with an epoxy resin. This type of BPP (with Nb as top-layer) was implemented in a PEMWE stack from Nel operated at 65°C with a current density of ca. 1.6 A/cm² [19] for 14000 hours with an average cell voltage degradation of around 5 μV/h.

2. Recent progresses towards stainless steel PTL

Corrosion of unprotected 316L was clearly evidenced by Mo *et al.* [20-21] who utilized a mesh of such stainless steel as simplified PTL in a PEMWE for a 15-hour experiment at 1 A/cm². Using SEM imaging, SEM-EDX and STEM-EDX analysis, the authors observed the “blossoming” of corrosion products at the PTL surface as well as iron contamination on both the anode and cathode sides. Those findings explained the fast degradation of the PEMWE performance.

Research on the protection stainless steel PTL is less abundant than that on BPP. This can be explained by the fact that it is more challenging to efficiently coat porous structures like PTL than (almost) flat elements, such as BPP. Only very recently, Stiber *et al.* protected a 316L PTL with a Nb/Ti bi-layer prepared by VPS (Figure 3) as a continuation of the investigations on BPP protection (Section 1) [22]. The outermost Nb film had the function of preventing the oxidation of titanium. Electrolysis operation at 65°C for 1400 hours was achieved at 2 A/cm². A steady increase of the PEMWE voltage was reported and assigned to the CCM (yet without investigating the causes in detail). The thick VPS coatings avoided, however, the massive cationic contamination obtained by Mo *et al.* with the unprotected stainless steel. It must also be noted that, in this experiment, closed-loop water reservoirs were used so as to concentrate the metallic ions due to the (potential) corrosion of the PTL within the electrolysis cell. This means that under “normal” PEMWE operations, the degradation rate might have been lower (though it was not experimentally proved in the paper).

Figure 3: SEM micrograph (cross-section) of a ca. 30 μm thick Nb/Ti coating deposited on 316L PTL by VPS. Reproduced from [22] under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

3. Perspectives

Recent progresses have demonstrated that BPP and PTL could be made of stainless steel provided that an appropriate (and cost-effective) corrosion protection is applied. Yet, the topic of the corrosion behavior of novel BPP, PTL and coatings is still understudied compared to other aspects of the PEMWE technology (like catalysts and polymer electrolyte membranes). Besides investigating new materials for BPP, PTL (like 316L) and coatings (such as TiN, CrN, C, Nb... [16,19,23]), several research areas are of great interest in the near future:

- At the fundamental level, the relationships between coating synthesis, microstructure and protective properties should be closely examined since the barrier properties are directly related to structural parameters, such as porosity, pore size, grain/column size, thickness...), as schematically depicted in Figure 4. Currently, even the studies reporting high-performance anti-corrosion coatings do not tackle this point (*i.e.* they present solely one coating without varying deposition conditions and microstructures). Studying the evolution of the microstructure after ex situ or in situ polarization could also bring relevant insights regarding the protection performance, notably to evaluate if corrosion products could be trapped in the coating pores or defects (such as pinholes), as described in Figure 4c. This would require high-resolution imaging techniques, such as FIB-SEM, STEM and nanotomography, as done in other areas of corrosion science [24-28], whereas these techniques are still utilized to a limited extent for BPP/PTL coating analysis [10,22]. This kind of investigations have been extensively carried out in other fields of hydrogen-based energy research, for instance for thin-film components in solid oxide fuel cells [29-31].

Figure 4: Sketch of the possible influence of the microstructure on the protective properties of a coating (here with the example of a columnar film, grey color). The corrosion products (orange color) are approximated to be iron cations from the stainless steel substrate (brown color). Reproduced from [1] under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

- At a higher technology readiness level, accelerated stress test (AST) should also be specifically developed for assessing the corrosion resistance and the durability of novel coated BPP and PTL in a realistic time frame in the lab. Such standard tests exist for several aspects of PEM fuel cell technology [32,33]. The closed-loop water feed aiming at concentrating the chemical elements (in forms of ions) originating from the corroded BPP, PTL and coatings constitutes an AST with water purity level as the stressor [22]. A particular relevant issue is the adhesion of the protective coatings. Long-term adhesion is one of the key-requirements for selecting a coating in addition to cost-effectiveness, chemical stability and protection against corrosion. Rakousky *et al.* demonstrated a degradation of electrolysis performance due to platinum layer delamination on titanium anode PTL at 3 A/cm² [12]. In that case, the high current density could be considered as the stressor. Finally, as PEMWE are viewed as suitable devices to be coupled with intermittent renewable sources (like sun or wind) due to their fast response times, AST with on/off phases (*i.e.* with change of current density and temperature) could be of significant interest [34]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, such AST investigations with a focus on coating adhesion has not been reported in the PEMWE literature yet.

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